

UNIVERSITY
OF APPLIED SCIENCES
UPPER AUSTRIA

RESIDUAL STRAIN DEVELOPMENT IN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED METAL HYBRID LAMINATS: AN EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION USING FBG STRAIN SENSORS

Maximilian Pollak, Michael Paulitsch and Roland M. Hinterhölzl

Contents

- **Introduction**
- **Measurement System**
- **Experiments**
- **Results**
- **Outlook**

Motivation

Transformation of Mobility – “Imp4Zero”

Non-destructive
characterization of
materials and
components in 3D

Arc detection

Damage detection and prevention in
lightweight
components

High-voltage
testing

[2]

faurecia
inspiring mobility

[1]

Motivation

Damage Detection

- Improve safety of battery box and H2 pressure vessels
- Increasing service life
- Enhance Quality control

[3]

[4]

[5]

Goals

- **Development of a measuring system for condition monitoring of structural composite components**
- **Condition monitoring:**
 - during manufacturing
 - of structural tests in the context of component development
 - online during operation
- **Investigation of the influence of sensor integration on mechanical performance**

Methods - Building Blocks

Methods - Building Blocks

FBG Introduction

- grating in the core of an optical fiber
- Small size $\varnothing 150 \mu\text{m}$, high sensitivity
- Acts as a wavelength-selective filter/mirror
- Sensitive to strain and temperature
- Wavelength shift:

$$\Delta\lambda_B = (1 - p_e)\Delta\varepsilon + (\alpha + \zeta)\Delta T$$

p_e ... photo – elastic constant

α ... coefficient of thermal expansion

ζ ... thermo – optic coefficient

Calibration Method

- In-situ calibration with embedded FBG and thermo-couple in tensile test rig with temperature chamber
- Strain calibration in range of $1500\mu\epsilon$
- Temperature in range $-40^{\circ}\text{C} - +180^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Temperature dependent CTE from TMA

Calibration Models

- **Emperical calibration model with least square**
- **Total sensitivity:** $(\lambda - \lambda_0)_{total} = (\lambda - \lambda_0)_{\varepsilon} + (\lambda - \lambda_0)_{\alpha} + (\lambda - \lambda_0)_T$
- **Strain sensitivity:** $(\lambda - \lambda_0)_{\varepsilon} = K_{\varepsilon} \Delta \varepsilon$
- **CTE sensitivity :** $(\lambda - \lambda_0)_{\alpha} = \alpha(T) \cdot \Delta T \cdot K_{\varepsilon}$
- **Temperature sensitivity :** $(\lambda - \lambda_0)_T = p_0 + p_1 \Delta T + p_2 \Delta T^2 + p_3 \Delta T^3 - \alpha(T) \cdot \Delta T \cdot K_{\varepsilon}$

Materials

TP-CFRP material:

- 0.2mm CF/PA6 Tape (SGL SIGRAPREG®TP C U157-0/NF-T340/46%)

Metal plates:

- 2mm stainless steel 1.4301
- 2mm aluminium plate EN AW-1050A

Adhesion promoter:

- Vestamelt Hylink (Evonik)

	Name	Layup	Sensor layer	Monitoring	Geometry
CFRP	symmetric-cross	$[0_2/90_2/0]_{2s}$	5/6	process	200x100x4mm
	unsymmetric cross	$[0_{12}/90_8]$	5/6	process	
Hybrid	CF/PA6-AL	$[0_{10}/AL_{2mm}]$	7/8	process, thermal cycling	
	CF/PA6-ST	$[0_{10}/ST_{2mm}]$	7/8	process, thermal cycling	
	cross-CF/PA6-AL	$[0_2 90_2/0_2/90_2/0_2/AL]$	7/8	process	
	cross-CF/PA6-ST	$[0_2 90_2/0_2/90_2/0_2/ST]$	7/8	process	

Process Monitoring

- Hot press mold with sensor feed-through
- FBG + TC embedded in stack
- 230°C and 100kN
- CFRP and Hybrids investigated

Thermal Cycling Test

- Climate chamber with sensor feed-through
- Aviation and Automotive cycle
- CF/PA6-ST and CF/PA6-AL specimens

Cycle	Automotive	Aviation
Temperatures	-40°C, 40°C, 80°C, 40°C	-40°C, 80°C
Hold time	10h	1,5h
Cycles	4.5	50
Total time	180h (7day 12h)	150h (6day 6h)
Material	CF/PA6-ST	CF/PA6-AL
specimens	4 200x100x4mm	4 Stk. 200x100x4mm
Heating rate	Cooling: -4°C/min +8°C/min	

Results - Process Monitoring

Process Monitoring CF/PA6-AL

Process Monitoring CF/PA6-ST

Results – Process Monitoring

Results – Process Monitoring

Comparison measured strain vs. simulated strain

	Material Combination	Measurement Strain [10 ⁻³]	Simulation Strain [10 ⁻³]
CFRP	[0 ₂ /90 ₂ /0 ₂ /90 ₂ /0 ₂] _s	-0.56	-0.55
		-0.49	-0.55
	[0 ₁₂ /90 ₈]*	-0.59	-0.37
CFRP-metal hybrid	[Al/0 ₁₀]	-0.68	-0.95
		-0.67	-0.95
	[Al/0 ₂ /90 ₂ /0 ₂ /90 ₂ /0 ₂]	-1.22	-1.30
		-1.17	-1.30
	[Steel/0 ₁₀]	-0.47	-0.85
		-0.47	-0.85
	[Steel/0 ₂ /90 ₂ /0 ₂ /90 ₂ /0 ₂]	-1.00	-1.30
	-1.27	-1.30	

Results - Thermal Cycling

- Investigated specimens
 - CF/PA6-ST (automotive)
 - CF/PA6-AL (aviation)
- No major relaxation observed

Automotive cycle

Aviation cycle

Automotive cycle

Results - Laser Scan

- 3D Laser scan of curved specimens
- Least-squares cylinder fitting
- Mean strain release 30-50 $\mu\epsilon$
- No release after cycling

Curvature measurements

State	Curvatures		Strains at FBG layer	
	ST-CF/PA6	AL-CF/PA6	ST-CF/PA6	AL-CF/PA6
After manufacturing	2.63E-3	5.05E-3	-2.15E-3	-3.23E-3
Bevor thermal cycling	3.22E-3	6.01E-3	-1.64E-3	-2.94E-3
After thermal cycling	3.34E-3	6.21E-3	-1.64E-3	-2.91E-3

Methods - Building Blocks

Simulation-Chain „As-built“

- Draping + Cure + Structural with mapped field variables
- Simulation „As-built“
- Mapping with user subroutines on intergration points

Results - "As-built" Simulation

- Matrix Tension in Region 1 caused by stress concentration at wrinkle
- Mesh size has major influence on concentration

crack propagation beneath loading pin

stress concentration observed in simulation and DIC

Results - "As-built" Simulation

- Comparison of reaction force of simulation and bending test
- Overestimated reaction force despite process induced effects
- Damage initialization of "As-built" agrees with test data

reaction force and Hashin criterion of simulation and bending test

Outlook

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Upper Austrian Government through the project:

“IMP4Zero-E: Innovative Monitoring- und Prüfverfahren für den Zero-Emission-Antriebsstrang“

and under its FTI Structural-Funding Program:

“Erforschung von Methoden für die Mobilität der Zukunft” (Project No. Wi-2018-466449/18-WieM)“

and by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG) through the “ProSim“ project (No. 866878).

Contact

Maximilian Pollak

maximilian.pollak@fh-wels.at

Thank you for your attention!

